

IMPROVING LEARNER’S LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS WITH THE HELP OF COMPETENT BASED LEARNING

Abdukhakimova K.A

(1st year Phd. student at Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11110690>

Abstract. This article demonstrates the gist meaning of competent based approach in teaching not only speaking but also listening skills. The most important notion of competent based approach will be explained below. Competent based learning is considered as an important tool for improving students’ acquisition in teaching listening and speaking skills.

Key words. CBL (competent based learning), EFL teachers, learners’ acquisition, skills, learned knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

The competency-based instruction (CBE) approach permits understudies to progress based on their capacity to ace an ability or competency at their claim pace notwithstanding of environment. This strategy is custom fitted to meet distinctive learning capacities and can lead to more effective understudy results.

Competency-based learning is based on clearly characterized and quantifiable learning targets or competencies. Understudies can illustrate authority of each competency through different evaluation shapes, such as ventures, expositions, and exams. They can moreover illustrate their learning through real-life encounters, such as internships or volunteer work. Once an understudy has illustrated dominance of a competency, they move on to the another one. This moreover permits for a personalized learning involvement, as understudies can center on their zones of quality and shortcomings and advance through the educational programs at their possess pace. Learner’s acquisition with the help of competent based approach will be boosted for student’s listening and speaking skills. Except from listening, speaking also the most valuable skills among learners, that’s why it’s ways in order to enhance both speaking and listening are recognized by educators.

Good listening skills are very important in today's connected world. Listening is not just about hearing, it is important for talking to others, building relationships, solving problems, and growing as a person. By improving how well you listen, you can be more successful at work, have better relationships, and help create a kinder and more understanding society. So, when you talk to someone, remember that listening is really important. Good communication is really important and can help make our relationships with others better, both at work and in our personal lives. Many of us try to communicate our thoughts and ideas well, but we forget how important it is to really listen and understand what others have to say. We can learn a lot, gain trust and avoid problems by being better at listening to others. At the same time, getting better at speaking can help us express our ideas better and make our audience interested. Understanding what you hear is very important when you are trying to learn a new language. It helps you understand people who speak the language natively, talk with them, and learn more about their language and culture. In this blog, we will look at good ways to get better at understanding a new language when you listen to it. If you follow these tips, you will become a better listener and feel more confident.

Is the Competency-Based Approach (CBA) the popular way of teaching language and literacy in the world today. The CBA is an advanced way of teaching English language. Competency means being able to use different skills and knowledge in different situations, even

if they are different from where you learned them. CBA connects what students learn in school to real-life situations so that learning is practical and long-lasting. The goal is for students to get smarter, improve their language skills, and become better at solving problems in school. This will help them handle difficult situations in and out of school. Students think that learning is important and helpful for their studies and future.

This method is based on the idea that teaching and learning go hand in hand. Therefore, when we talk about a teacher's abilities, we are looking at how they help students learn and improve their English skills. The teacher needs to learn how to think about their teaching and figure out if it's working. They should also learn new ways to teach that can help students get better at English. So, knowing how to use language for speaking, listening, reading, and writing is really important in school. Students learn how to listen, speak, read, and write, and also how to use the language in different ways. The goal is to encourage students to take charge of their own learning and be responsible and independent in their development. Teachers teach these skills together because that's how people use them in real life.

Simple tips for getting better at listening. It is important to get better at listening so you can communicate better. Here are some things you can do to be a better listener: Rewrite this text in easier words: 1. "The presentation was very comprehensive and covered a wide range of topics. " "The presentation covered a lot of information on many different topics. " Be alert One of the most important parts of being a good listener is to focus and pay attention. Pay attention to the speaker and don't get distracted. Keep your phone out of sight, turn off the TV, and listen to the speaker without any distractions. "Rewrite this text in simple words: 2. "Can you simplify this text for me. Asking questions can help you understand what the speaker is saying and show that you are interested in the conversation. Ask questions that allow the speaker to explain their ideas more. Please rewrite your text for me to simplify. Rewrite this text using easier words. Paraphrasing means to say something that someone else said in your own way. It can help you make sure you understand what the speaker is saying and show that you are paying attention.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.teachnews.gr/glwssologia-didaktikh/>
2. [2.https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/competency-based-teaching-approach](https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/competency-based-teaching-approach)
3. <https://medium.com/@atlasrelics/improving-your-listening>